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Numerical investigation of geometric effects and mass property on the performance of torpedo anchor deep-water mooring systems for marine hydrokinetic devices in sandy seabeds.

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Abstract

Marine hydrokinetic (MHK) energy is a renewable energy source to support decarbonization and has potential resources in deep water environments, such as in the case of the Gulf Stream current. This has created a need for efficient and cost-effective anchoring solutions in deepwater, with torpedo anchors emerging as a promising option due to their simple deployment in deepwater through free-fall installation. Torpedo anchors have recently gained attention in the industry, but limited research has been dedicated towards identifying characteristics associated with improved performance in sandy seabeds. This study investigates the influence of geometric parameters including slenderness ratio (L/D) and fin length, and mass, on the penetration depth and pull-out resistance of torpedo anchors. Numerical simulations reveal that, despite their increased mass, anchors with lower L/D ratios exhibit reduced penetration due to increased frictional resistance on larger surface areas and fin-induced drag. Pull-out capacity, however, peaks at moderate L/D values, indicating an optimal balance between embedment depth and pull-out resistance. Fin length affects performance: shorter fins enhance penetration, while moderate fin lengths yield maximum pull-out. The equivalent plastic strain distribution confirms significant soil deformation near the tip and shaft. These findings provide guidance for optimizing torpedo anchors in sandy seabeds.

Keywords: torpedo anchor; slenderness ratio; fin length; penetration depth; pull-out capacity

1. Introduction

The United States is advancing marine hydrokinetic (MHK) energy to meet decarbonization goals and enhance energy security. MHK technologies, which harness the power of ocean and river currents, waves, and tidal streams, have the potential to generate a substantial amount of clean energy. MHK devices often require reliable mooring systems to remain in place, especially since several MHK anchoring sites are in deep waters. Conventional systems

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like suction or pile foundations face challenges in deep water due to high costs, complex deployment, and environmental concerns. As a result, torpedo anchors have emerged as a promising alternative, offering simpler, cost-effective anchoring for renewable energy devices in deep-sea environments[1].

Mooring systems and anchors play a crucial role in the protection of floating marine structures, including offshore platforms and renewable energy devices[2]. Various types of mooring lines and anchors have been used to secure marine structures, with shared mooring systems becoming more common for MHK energy devices [3]. The behavior of cables, anchor types, and their applications have been extensively studied [4], and traditional anchor types such as those used in single-anchor, single-line systems for meteorological buoys, continue to be used in simpler mooring applications[4]. New anchor technologies, such as vertical plate anchors, are being developed to offer high efficiency and installation benefits for wave energy devices in coarse-grained soils[5]. Recent advancements in deep-water environments have made torpedo anchors economical and reliable for offshore applications[1].

Torpedo anchors represent a special class of vertically penetrating anchors designed to achieve significant embedment into the seabed through free fall from a designated height. A typical configuration for the dynamically installed torpedo anchor used in this study is shown in Figure 1(a), and consists of four parts [6]: the pad-eye that connects the first segment of the mooring line to the anchor, a ballasted carbon steel shaft, four fins or flukes, and a conical tip designed to improve the penetration performance of the anchor[7]. Most existing studies on torpedo anchors have focused on their application in clay soils, with relatively few studies of their performance in sandy environments. This study, therefore, aims to investigate the performance of torpedo anchors in sandy soils, with the ultimate goal of informing the design and evaluation of these anchors for the deep-water anchoring of marine energy devices. We will use the tools of numerical simulation to develop finite element models and consider the effect of varying geometric parameters including slenderness ratio fin size as well as mass properties on embedment depth and pullout resistance in saturated soils. We will also assess the impact of soil saturation by comparing results in saturated and unsaturated sandy soils.

2. Methodology

We developed a finite element model for simulating the dynamic analysis of torpedo anchor installation and pull-out using the Abaqus software [8]. The dynamic simulation involved dropping the anchor from a height of 6.096 m (20 ft) above the soil test pit and tracking its penetration behavior, including final embedment depth and subsequent pull-out resistance. We adopted surface-to-surface contact for the interface interaction to incorporate both tangential and normal behaviors. Tangential interaction was defined by a penalty friction model with a coefficient of 0.3, allowing limited slip before full sliding. We modeled the normal behavior using hard contact to prevent interpenetration between different bodies while permitting separation, and we used the default kinematic constraint enforcement for numerical stability. We constrained the soil boundaries to prevent radial movement and fully fixed the base in translation. The soil followed the Mohr-Coulomb failure criterion, capturing shear strength through cohesion and friction angle. We treated the anchor as a rigid body, with motion limited to vertical translation only. Both the soil test pit and the anchor were meshed with linear hexahedral elements of type C3D8R, and we used the dynamic explicit solver which is suitable for modeling impact and penetration.

2.1 Model parameters

The torpedo anchor considered in this study is made from high-strength stainless steel, with a density of 7500 kg/m^3 , a Young's modulus of 200 GPa, and a Poisson's ratio of 0.3. The anchor consists of a pad-eye for connection, a cylindrical shaft, a conical tip, and four trapezoidal fins which are functions of the length L and diameter d of the anchor and having a non-parallel edge inclined at a 45° angle relative to the base as shown in Figure 1(b). The choice of this torpedo anchor geometry is premised on its performance and usage in an earlier research [7]. A review of previous studies shows that full-scale torpedo anchors typically range from 12 to 17 meters in length with shaft diameters between 0.76 and 1.1 meters. Laboratory-scale models, typically at a 1:20 scale, have lengths between 0.6 and 0.85 meters and shaft diameters of 0.038 to 0.055 meters. These dimensions are selected to achieve realistic embedment behavior and maintain dynamic similarity by preserving the slenderness ratio (L/D). In this study, we

begin with an even smaller 1:30 scale and progressively increase the prototype size to identify an optimal design configuration that will be validated with an experiment in our Constructed Facility Laboratory (CFL).

Fig. 1. (a) Torpedo anchor; (b) Geometric parameters of the anchor [7]

The CFL has a circular soil pit with a diameter of 3.048 m (10 ft) and a depth of 6.096 m (20 ft). The soil within the pit is modeled based on laboratory characterization at a relative density of 20%. In the unsaturated condition, the soil exhibits a dry unit weight of 14.9 kN/m^3 , a Young's modulus of 10.75 MPa, a Poisson's ratio of 0.3, cohesion of 0.1 kPa, a friction angle of 30° , and a void ratio of 0.75. Under saturated conditions, the unit weight is 19.1 kN/m^3 , while the cohesion and friction angle are 0.01 kPa and 28° , respectively. While MHK devices are installed in saturated seabeds, studying unsaturated conditions provides insight into anchor performance in transitional zones such as tidal flats and estuaries where saturation may vary seasonally or with tidal cycles. Also, including unsaturated simulations contributes new data and understanding to an area with limited research, strengthening the scientific foundation for future designs.

2.2 Prediction of torpedo anchor penetration and holding capacity in clay

To verify our modeling approach, we first simulated torpedo anchor penetration in clay using Abaqus and compared the results with an established analytical solution [1]. In clay, the penetration depth and pull out capacity of torpedo anchors can be predicted using a nonlinear dynamic equation that accounts for the resistance soils [1] as follows:

$$m \frac{d^2z}{dt^2} = W_s - F_y - R_f(F_b + F_f) - F_d$$

where m is the mass of the anchor, W_s is the submerged weight, F_y is the buoyant force, R_f is a rate dependent factor, F_d is the drag force, F_b is the base or bearing resistance, and F_f is the side frictional resistance. This formulation was solved in Matlab for a T-98 model with a mass of 98 tonnes, a diameter of 1.07m, length of 17m and four trapezoidal fins of $10 \times 0.9\text{m}$. The clay soil has an undrained shear strength of $S_u = 5 + 2z \text{ kPa}$, where z is the depth in meters.

Figure 2 shows that the of the finite elements simulation are in close agreement with the analytical solution. With an impact velocity of 26.8 m/s, the obtained final penetration depth of 30m, shown in Figure 2, agrees with the empirical correlation proposed by Brandão et al. [9]. From Figure 2(b), we see that as S_u increases, both the bearing and the friction resistance increase, with the F_f having a larger value since the shaft area is significantly larger than the base area. At high velocity, the drag contributes to the resistance and gradually diminishes until the velocity becomes zero. Both the submerged weight and buoyant force remains unchanged since the anchor's weight and volume remains constant. The same model is simulated in Abaqus with a result in agreement with what is obtained from solving the analytical equation numerically. This result confirms the accuracy of the numerical modeling approach and sets the stage for its application to sandy soils under various conditions.

Fig. 2. (a) Penetration depth and anchor velocity with time; and (b) Pullout force with time

3. Results

3.1 Parametric study: Numerical model of torpedo anchor in both saturated and an unsaturated sandy soils

In this parametric study, we investigated the influence of key geometric parameters on the performance of torpedo anchors in sandy soils under both saturated and unsaturated conditions. In set A1–A5, we varied the slenderness ratio (L/D) by adjusting anchor length and diameter while keeping mass nearly constant. For set A5–A9, we examined the effect of fin length on penetration and pull-out resistance, and in set B1–B5, we explored the influence of varying the L/D ratio while maintaining constant length. In each case, only one parameter is varied at a time to isolate its effect, while others are held constant due to their interdependence. Penetration depth and pull-out resistance are measured from simulation results, providing insight into how geometric modifications impact anchor behavior and guiding the design of efficient anchors for MHK applications.

Effect of constant mass: Consider the configurations of torpedo anchors given in Table 1 below with an approximately constant mass (M) and varying slenderness ratio (L/D). This approach allows for a focused evaluation of how slenderness ratio affects the penetration depth (Z) and pull-out capacity in both unsaturated (unsat) and saturated (sat) conditions.

Table 1. Effect of constant mass.

Design	L(cm)	D (cm)	L/D	Fin width (cm)	M (kg)	Z (unsat, cm)	Z (sat, cm)	Pull-out (unsat, N)	Pull-out (sat, N)
A1	38	6.2	6.13	0.1	7.27	14.4	23.45	90	107
A2	40	6	8.33	0.1	7.33	11.69	43.25	249	139
A3	45	5.5	8.18	0.1	7.25	18.68	26.24	234	177
A4	50	5.3	9.43	0.1	7.67	23.56	45.48	257	212
A5	55	5	11	0.1	7.7	33.25	40.74	209	284

The result indicate that penetration depth increases with increasing L/D , particularly in unsaturated soil. This is due to slender anchors with high L/D having a smaller cross-sectional area and reduced drag resistance enabling deeper penetration under free fall. Lower L/D configurations show reduced penetration despite having the same mass, due to the high frictional resistance on the shaft's surface area. The pull-out capacity initially in unsaturated conditions initially increased with L/D and decline beyond a certain L/D value, which suggests that while deeper penetration provides better pull-out resistance, excessively slender geometries may reduce bearing area and lateral resistance during extraction. In saturated soils, pull-out capacity increases with L/D due to increasing penetration depth and reducing effective stress of the soil.

Effect of fin length: To investigate the effect of fin length on torpedo anchor behavior, a series of anchors with progressively shorter fins ($2/3L$, $1/2L$, $1/3L$, $1/4L$, $0L$) positioned near the padeye were analyzed while keeping the overall geometry consistent, as shown in Table 2. As fin length decreases, the mass showed a slight reduction, but its

influence on performance was secondary to the effects of drag and lateral resistance. Penetration depth increased significantly with shorter fins, with the finless anchor achieving multiples values of the embedment depth of the longest-fin design, driven primarily by reduced aerodynamic and soil resistance. This trend is observed in both saturated and unsaturated soils, though embedment was generally deeper in saturated conditions due to lower soil strength. Pull-out capacity varied non-monotonically: in unsaturated soil, it peaked at a short fin length before dropping sharply when fins were removed, while in saturated soil, maximum pull-out occurred at a moderate fin length. This behavior is because of the interplay between soil strength and embedment depth. Saturated soils allow deeper penetration, which enhances pull-out resistance by increasing frictional contact. In contrast, unsaturated soils offer higher shear strength, but this also limits penetration, resulting in shallower embedment and reduced resistance. As a result, unsaturated anchors occasionally has higher pull-out capacity than saturated ones when a favorable balance between embedment and soil strength is achieved. Notably, the finless torpedo, despite achieving the deepest penetration, results in poor pull-out performance when compared to the finned anchor.

Table 2. Effect of fin length.

Design	L(cm)	D (cm)	L/D	Fin width (cm)	Fin length (cm)	M (kg)	Z (unsat, cm)	Z (sat, cm)	Pull-out (unsat, N)	Pull-out (sat, N)
A5	55	5	11	0.1	36.67	7.70	33.25	40.74	209	284
A6	55	5	11	0.1	27.50	7.56	39.49	56.15	150	233
A7	55	5	11	0.1	18.33	7.42	46.19	63.66	225	321
A8	55	5	11	0.1	13.75	7.35	45.05	70.03	263	254
A9	55	5	11	0.1	0	7.18	97.78	149.61	135	212

Effect of constant length: This part gives the results of how the diameter-driven changes in the geometry affect the anchor's behavior during penetration and pull-out when the length is fixed, as presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of constant length.

Design	L(cm)	D (cm)	L/D	Fin width (cm)	M (kg)	Z (unsat, cm)	Z (sat, cm)	Pull-out (unsat, N)	Pull-out (sat, N)
B1	80	4	20	0.1	8	60.31	69.47	160	240
B2	80	5	16	0.1	11	70.68	99.93	249	274
B3	80	5.5	14.54	0.1	13	49.97	57.35	274	317
B4	80	6	13.33	0.1	16.29	45.90	87.29	373	368
B5	80	8	10	0.1	27.59	41.29	49.37	524	222

As the L/D ratio decreased (i.e., diameter increased), the mass and the impact kinetic energy of the anchors increased significantly. However, rather than promoting deeper embedment, the penetration depth actually decreased in both unsaturated and saturated soils with decreasing L/D, due to the larger frontal area of lower L/D anchors as a result of the fins, which introduce greater soil resistance during penetration, outweighing the benefit of increased mass. The pull-out, however, increased in unsaturated soil. For unsaturated soils, the pull-out peaked at moderate L/D values, suggesting that excessive mass and base area may lead to reduced effectiveness in generating suction or friction.

3.2 Stress distribution and failure mechanism around the anchor

The PEEQ (equivalent plastic strain) field provides insight into the extent of permanent deformation in the soil around the anchor tip. Figure 3 displays the PEEQ distribution for the saturated B2 configuration in Table 3 with full embedment. The results show that PEEQ concentrations are highest immediately beneath and around the tip after penetration, indicating intense plastic shearing and compaction as the anchor displaces the soil, as given in Figure 3(a). The plastic zone spreads downward and radially outward from the tip. After pull-out, the PEEQ distribution reveals residual plastic zones that remain in the wake of the anchor, particularly along the shaft path and near the tip, as shown in Figure 3(b). These residual strains signify irreversible soil disturbance, and are more pronounced for a

deep embedment or when the anchor mobilizes significant frictional resistance during pull-out. The presence and extent of these PEEQ zones are important for understanding soil softening, potential remolding, and changes in strength during loading or reinstallation scenarios. In general, higher strain gradients are expected in unsaturated soil due to greater shear resistance.

Fig. 3. Equivalent plastic strain distribution for B2 anchor (a) after penetration, and (b) after complete pull-out of the anchor

To ensure the simulation accurately captures this behavior, the model is configured to handle large deformation through Abaqus's nonlinear geometry setting[8], which allows the finite element solver to update strains and displacements relative to the deformed configuration. This enables realistic tracking of large plastic strains, severe distortion, and evolving contact conditions as the anchor penetrates and interacts with the surrounding soil.

4. Conclusion

This study explored the influence of geometric parameters including slenderness ratio and fin length on the performance of torpedo anchors in both saturated and unsaturated soils using simulation-based analysis. Results showed that reducing fin length significantly enhances penetration depth due to reduced drag forces, with the deepest embedment occurring in finless configurations. However, pull-out capacity exhibited a non-monotonic trend, peaking at moderate fin lengths where a balance between embedment depth and anchorage resistance is achieved. In contrast, very long fins reduce penetration with some limited improvement in pull-out, and finless designs, despite deep embedment, provide poor uplift resistance. When anchor length was held constant, increasing diameter (i.e., decreasing L/D) resulted in greater mass and higher impact kinetic energy. However, contrary to expectations, penetration depth decreased with decreasing L/D in both soil types. This was primarily due to the increased surface area and associated drag, especially from fins, which outweighed the benefits of increased mass during penetration. Despite shallower embedment, pull-out capacity increased in unsaturated soil, with a peak occurring at moderate L/D values—indicating that there is an optimal geometry that balances mass, bearing area, and suction mobilization. The equivalent plastic strain (PEEQ) distribution revealed localized soil failure around the anchor tip during penetration and permanent deformation along the shaft after pull-out, reflecting significant soil disturbance and residual plastic strains. While these findings offer valuable design insights, future work would be dedicated to validating these trends through controlled laboratory experiments, particularly to assess the predictions and the soil-structure interaction during dynamic embedment and extraction.

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